

THE STUDY OF ACOUSTIC EMISSION FROM COMPOSITES BY MEANS OF MULTIVARIATE DATA ANALYSIS

Mohammed Cherfaoui - James Roget
Alain Lemaçon - Max Jeanville
CETIM (Centre Technique des Industries Mécaniques)
52 avenue Félix Louat - B.P. 67
60304 SENLIS CEDEX
FRANCE

ABSTRACT

This paper describes some tests which were performed on unidirectional composite specimens (fiberglass, epoxy). The influence of intentional defects (porosity, delamination, aging of base material) on the Acoustic Emission behaviour during embedded bending tests was studied. The analysis of classical Acoustic Emission parameters such as activity (number of Events) and count number, may succeed to characterize the quality of the specimen as it was shown in a previous paper.

In fact, various types of signals may appear indicating that several sources of Acoustic Emission are simultaneously activated. This type of analysis needs to get individual characteristics of the signals and to apply statistical methods. Multivariate data analysis are in these conditions very powerful. They take into account all the parameters and point out hidden correlations between signals, their characteristics and mechanical parameters.

This paper shows an example of the application of factorial analysis and automatic classification method. Typical step and information which can be obtained are pointed out.

INTRODUCTION

The development of composite structural parts requires that the eventual defects can be detected and their behaviour under sollicitation predicted.

In composite structures, usual NDT methods (X-Rays, Ultrasonics ...) can reveal some types of defects (blow, delamination ...) and sometimes they can give their size but they never graduate their nocivity.

On the contrary, Acoustic Emission does not aim at sizing the defects, but informs on internal damage of the structure, and on the nocivity of the defect under the applied loading. That explains the interest of the composite designers and users for this technique.

Previous papers [1-2] have shown the results obtained from the analysis of the classical parameters such as event number, count number, peak amplitude.

Several criteria on AE analysis allowed to separate standard and defective specimens according to their internal damage. This analysis does not take into account the characteristics of the individual signals while signals of various patterns were observed, indicating that several source mechanisms might be activated.

This paper describes the results of another analysis :

- AE signals were digitized ;
- Their spectral content was determined ;
- Multivariate data analysis and automatic classification methods were applied to extract the maximum information from these data.

The usefulness of these methods is discussed mainly for feasibility studies.

EXPERIMENTAL ARRANGEMENT

Specimens.

Special plates were made by hot compression of SMC unidirectional glass-epoxy. Five plates were made with various conditions :

Series 3	Normal moulding conditions
5	Creation of distributed defects (porosity)
6	Introduction of a delamination (teflon)
7	Introduction of a crease of SMC sheet
8	Use of an aged and wet base material

Testing conditions.

Bending tests were carried out at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min and with a special testing fixture as shown in figure 1. Load and displacement were continuously recorded during the test. In each plate, several specimens were removed and up to fracture.

Figure 1. Test-set up.

Acoustic Emission (AE instrumentation).

Online, a classical system measures counts and burst numbers, peak amplitude and RMS value. Simultaneously, AE signals are stored on magnetic tape (1 MHz band pass) for post analysis (digitization and frequency analysis).

ACOUSTIC EMISSION CRITERIA

It appeared that AE was able to separate the specimens according to their internal state, so AE criteria were proposed in this goal.

The early damage stage was first investigated. For example, correlations between ultimate load of the specimen and critical loads corresponding to 5, 10,

20, 40, 100, 150 and 300 bursts were examined. Figure 2a is an example of such a correlation. The abscissa is the difference between the load corresponding to 300 bursts and that corresponding to 100 bursts. It can be seen that series 7 (x), series 8 () and series 3, 5 () are clearly separated. Series 6 specimens () may be classified as sound or defective according to the place of the defect, ie according to the stress actually applied to the defect.

Figure 2. Correlation between mechanical characteristics and AE early activity.

Another correlation is presented in figure 2b : Yield strength is plotted against the activity recorded during loading up to 200 daN. Some results are obtained.

All these results correspond to an early phase of the test ; a qualitative evaluation of the specimen can be made at about half the yield strength (no damaging level) which is very interesting for a non-destructive examination.

APPLICATION OF MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS

General procedure

The previous results relate to global analysis of AE activity. The specific shapes of the AE signals are not considered while they may be largely different as shown by figure 3. Several parameters are necessary to quantify these differences of the AE pattern, and statistics are necessary to extract useful information of this big amount of data.

Data analysis methods are special statistical methods. They can be divided in two branches :

- The factorial analyses aim at a simplified plotting, which makes the explanation easier, and points out correlation between data, parameters, data and parameters ;
- The classification methods which aim to cluster the signals into homogeneous classes, ie in a given class all the signals have near characteristics. Typical methods are the k-nearest neighbours and dynamic clouds.

Figure 3. Some actual AE signals.

CETIM has got a software library including a lot of data analysis algorithms. First, applications to AE data from fatigue test research showed that these methods are very powerful in scientific research. They can reveal masked correlations between signals, their characteristics and loading parameters. In this way, they may be very useful for the interpretation of experimental results.

In the present case, each AE signal is characterized by 9 parameters which are the power spectral densities in 9 frequency bands (V1 : 50-100 kHz - V2 : 100-150 kHz - V9 : 450-500 kHz). Therefore, each signal may be considered as a reactor in a 9-dimension space; the components of this vector are the measured parameters. All the data constitute a cloud which is not easy to interpret. The aim of multivariate data analysis is to reduce the number of dimensions without losing much information. Examples of applications are presented hereafter.

Bending test up to fraction : Standard specimen (without defect)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used. It aims at determining the main significant axes (more information) and to project the initial data on every plane defined by 2 axes.

The algorithm gives also indication on statistical significance of parameters and on correlation between them. Example is given below :

. Statistical results

Though a wideband transducer was used, the parameters V1, V2, V3 which cover the frequency-band 50-200 kHz are the most scattered and contain the most part of energy. This can be explained by the fact that the transducer is not perfectly wideband and presents a resonance at 200 kHz.

. Correlation between parameters

No correlation exists between the parameters (correlation factor 0,52) That means all the parameters (V1 to V9) are useful for discriminating the different types of signals.

. Determination of the main factors

The first axis is varying in the same sense as all the parameters (positive correlations) and is strongly correlated with V1 to V6 especially V3 (0,77) and V4 (0,78). It may be considered as representing the energy of the signal because the most part of energy is included in V1 to V6.

The second axis is well correlated with lower energy frequency band (V7, V8, V9), ie higher frequencies.

. Factorial plane : axis 1 - axis 2

The projection of the initial data on this plane, is presented in figure 4. It keeps 44 % of the initial information content.

It can be seen that dots are distributed along the axis 1, which means their energy is quite different. No more explanation can be simply deduced. So an automatic classification was applied (hierarchical ascendand classification).

3 classes were identified, as it can be seen on figure 4. These 3 classes can be explained by signals generated by 3 different phenomena.

- Class NR 1 (+) contains signals with a high energy content in the 5 first frequency bands. These signals might be associated with a high internal damage mechanism ;

- Class NR 2 (*) is distributed along the axis 2 and signals have small values on the axis 1 : Associated signals have been identified coming from the generalized damage zone. These signals present low energy and high frequency (350-400 kHz) content ;

- Class NR 3 (O) gathers medium signals. They have been associated with the zone of early damage.

Figure 4. Principal Component Analysis and cluster analysis Standard specimen
+ class NR 1 O class NR 2 * class NR 3

It should be added that classes are not time dependent, ie signals of the 3 classes appear simultaneously during the whole duration of the test. In other words, the associated damaging mechanisms are activated all test long.

This partition in 3 classes was confirmed by other processings ; that means they have a physical meaning, and there are probably 3 separate AE source mechanisms.

Bending test up to fraction : Defective specimen

The same processing technique was applied to the AE data issued from a defective specimen (aged and wet base material). Figure 5 presents the projection of all the data on the plane axis 1 - axis 2. Dots are separated in four classes according to the result of the classification analysis.

In fact, observation of the characteristics of the signals leads to the following conclusions :

- . Classes NR 1, 2 and 3 are the same as in the previous specimen ;
- . Class NR 4 gathers signals very similar to those of the class NR 3 and may be considered as a subclass of NR 3.

In conclusion, data analyses showed that the same AE source mechanisms are activated in all specimens (whatever the initial state of damage). This result seems natural when the bending test goes up to fracture. In the following step, only AE emitted during elastic deformation was studied.

Figure 5. Principal Component Analysis and cluster analysis damaged specimen (series 8).

+ class NR 1 * class NR 2 O class NR 3 x class NR 4

Study of the Elastic data

With the objective of non-destructive application, only AE data generated during the elastic phase (theoretically non damaging) are interesting.

Consequently, Elastic AE data of 4 specimens were analyzed. Another classification algorithm was used (dynamic clouds). It allows a partition of the initial data, while keeping the serial number of each signal.

Figure 6 presents the results for 4 specimens : 1 standard and 3 with different defects. The x axis is the serial number of the AE signals.

Following remarks can be made :

- in the standard specimen (figure 6a). There are only 3 classes at the beginning of the test. Classes NR 1 and 4 are predominant ;

- in the 3 defective specimens (figure 6b, 6c, 6d), 4 classes are pointed out. The class NR 3 can therefore be associated with the presence of a defect whatever the nature of this defect ;

- the 4 plots correspond to AE data detected at the same loading level. It can be seen that the number of signals is larger in the defective specimens.

In conclusion, this type of analysis points out that defective specimens can be distinguished very soon by looking for signals of class 3 during a low-load test. Corresponding signals may be identified by determining their specific parameters.

Figure 6. Dynamic Cloud Methods : Applications to AE data from 4 specimens (loading up to 200 daN)

Comparative study of the 4 specimens

The specimens do not show the same behaviour according to the nature and position of the defects. To compare the 4 specimens, a global analysis of all the AE data from these 4 specimens were simultaneously processed. Then, it was necessary to consider the following remarks.

- 1 - Experimental testing conditions are never identical (influence of the operator and of the apparatus) and results of the analysis may be affected. Consequently, it was chosen to replace absolute energy by relative energy : for each signal, the value of energy in each frequency band is divided by the total energy of the signal.
- 2 - The total number of signals for the 4 tests was too large. So, it was decided to cluster the signals in groups of 5 signals and each group was replaced by its center of gravity.

A principal component analysis was applied to these data. Figure 7 presents the projection on the plane 1 and 2.

Following remarks may be made :

- data from specimen LS 88 (x) are quite separated. They gathered around V1, V2 and V3 ; that means that signals have high values of these parameters (low frequency content) ;

- signals from specimen LS 69 are between V4, V5, V6 and V9. They have high frequency content (V9) and medium (V4, V5, V6) ;

- signals from specimen LS 36 are placed around V7. Therefore they have a high value of energy in the corresponding frequency band (350-400 kHz) ;

- signals from specimen LS 77 show a large scattering ; some of them are near V2 - V3 (lower frequency) and others are near V4 - V5 (higher frequency).

In fact, with a single processing, it was possible to characterize the behaviour of each type of specimen according to the frequency content of the signals. It would be possible to examine more thoroughly the results to confirm the observed behaviours but a general tendency is immediately pointed out, which facilitates later analysis and interpretation.

Figure 7. Principal Component Analysis - AE data from 4 specimens loaded to yield point
+ LS 36 * LS 69 O LS 77 x LS 88

DISCUSSION

These works aimed at determining whether AE monitoring can give information on eventual defects and internal damaging zones, are there specific signals of AE ? To answer this question, it was chosen to apply multivariate data analysis : factorial analysis and classification methods. These methods have shown that specific signals of AE appear very early in the test when defects exist in the materials.

This result is very important for developing a non-destructive examination method, because identification of these signals during a test at low load, is significant of a defect. It is then possible to develop a system looking for these signals, characteristics of which a system can be determined.

A second result is that there are 3 different types of signals, appearing in a standard specimen. They could be related to 3 different damaging mechanisms, for example : fiber cracking, fiber debonding, matrix crazing. Other works are necessary to correlate these types of signals with the physical sources.

The examples which were presented above, are partial results of a large work on AE examination of composites. They clearly pointed out the interest of data analyses which allow to study the simultaneous influence of many varying parameters. It is then possible with few tests to get maximum information, statistically significant.

The development of these analyses can solve the problem of using the mass of data given by sophisticated equipment (digitizer, multiparameter measurement).

Their use in feasibility study can help to choose significant measurements and to interpretate, in terms of statistics, the meaning of experimental data.

CONCLUSION

By measuring characteristics of individual AE signals, and using multivariate data analysis, it was possible to demonstrate that defective specimens and safe specimens have different behaviours. A specific type of signal was related to the presence of a defect. If it is possible to identify these signals, in real-time, a separation of sound and defective specimens is easy to perform.

Generally speaking, data analyses are very powerful processing techniques, able to extract the highest amount of information from experimental data. They look essential when equipments become more and more sophisticated and measure a great number of characteristics.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Cherfaoui, A. Lemasçon, J. Roget, D. Noiret "Suivi par Emission Acoustique du comportement en flexion d'un matériau verre epoxyde unidirectionnel" Composites, n° 3 - Mai-juin 1986.
- [2] M. Cherfaoui, A. Lemasçon, J. Roget, D. Noiret "Detection and evaluation of defects in unidirectional FRP by Acoustic Emission monitoring of Bending tests". The 8th International Acoustic Emission Symposium, Tokyo, Japan - Progress in Acoustic Emission III, 1986.